

Design and Emotion: Supra-Functionality for Engineers

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Abstract

This paper offers an insight into the engineering design practitioners' view on the integration of supra-functionality in their own design practice. It will discuss how practitioners may adopt an emotionally intelligent design approach to support future projects, with the aim of improving their commercial return and enhancing the total user experience.

Responding to supra-functional needs of users, such as their emotional and cultural requirements is fundamental to the success of a product. Providing satisfactory function alone does not necessarily lead to product acceptance or use. Few engineering designers appreciate the added value of emotionally aware design and may find it difficult to develop successful user-centred products.

Tools for integrating supra-functionality may share the same title from one project to the next but can be extremely different in content for each product or system. A flexible approach needs to become an integral part of the engineering design process, applied holistically and integrated with the engineers' pre-defined sources of information.

Engineers quite often work in isolation with minimal input from industrial designer or consumers in the design process. The late involvement of the user within the design process results in the product foundation being laid down without consideration to users' supra-functional needs. This paper discusses the engineers' view of supra-functionality at a philosophical level and in its practical application. The discussion will be based on a focus group session and one-to-one interviews with a sample of design engineers.

Keywords: Engineering Designer, Human Centred-Design, Supra-functionality, Emotion

Introduction

Engineers are responsible for designing some of the world's most complex systems in power transmission, solid mechanics, thermo and fluid dynamics. Even at this complex level of engineering, a supra-functional approach would enhance and support a more effective outcome. Supra-functionality can be further described as the element of a product, system or service that meets the total qualitative human factors of emotion, cultural, social and human behaviour, it places emphasis on providing a fulfilling experience for the user whilst meeting the wants and desires of particular user groups.

Design as research is a rational practice, but it is one in which emotion is allowed its own power and intelligence (Lunenfield 2003).

The authors comprise an Engineering designer and Industrial designer. Within Industrial design significant advances have been made in integrating the user and responding to the emotional domain. For Engineering designers, the emotional domain has not yet fully embraced as a contributory factor to product success. A study was conducted with participants from a broad range of professional engineering backgrounds, with over 160 years collective professional experience in engineering design. From this study the authors intended to reveal the engineering design practitioners' views on the emotional domain in design, to help identify any actual or perceived barriers that may exist.

The study used a focus group discussion and survey to collect the data. The focus group provided data of a qualitative nature such as the design engineers' views and perceptions of supra-functionality. Furthermore, the survey provided quantitative data with engineering designers rating their level of agreement to pre-set statements on supra-functionality. A comparison of the data helped to ensure that the focus group provided a true account of the individual design engineers' views and did not represent a politically correct viewpoint influenced by peers in the group or other senior members. Findings from this study provide both the engineering designer and design educators with useful guidelines for exploring and integrating a more supra-functional design approach.

Background

Considering the emotional elements within product design and development is a growing activity based on the realisation that they can have a significant impact on product success.

Product developers, manufacturers and designers are slowly identifying that qualitative aspects are crucial to product success. A positive user experience is sustained through a thorough understanding of consumer needs, emotional bonding, product semantics and user expectations beyond the functional, taking into account various behavioural modes of specific user groups.

Phillips, Apple Macintosh and Sony have identified these qualitative aspects as crucial to a product's success in the market and have asked designers to address this. The product semantics, emotional bonds and cultural significance contribute to a consumer's relationship with any given product. The model of the designing process is changing as it integrates the

user within and throughout the process (McDonagh-Philp and Lebbon 2000) and with it the role of the designer (McDonagh-Philp and Denton 1999).

Current literature highlights a need for the engineering designer to embrace supra-functional needs (McKim, 2001. Norden Guldbrandsen, 2003. Burns and Evans, 2000. Denning, 2002) There is much literature that discusses the importance of designing for a particular user experience, (Hekkert and McDonagh, 2003. Bruseberg and McDonagh-Philp, 2002 and Desmet, Overbeeke, and Tax, 2001) the benefits of considering consumer emotional needs and its positive effect on sales (McDonagh-Philp and Lebbon 2000), brand loyalty (Landmann, Wolters et al, 2001. and Stompff, 2003) and competitive advantage over other less supra-functional products. Tools enabling design engineers' to adopt and implement supra-functionality, need to be made available to support this plethora of motivating and enthusiastic research. There is a distinct difference between knowing and doing (Pfeffer and Sutton 2000).

Research has been carried out, by the authors, to identify what actual or perceived barriers exist in designing for a user experience. Until the engineering design practitioner understands both the importance of supra-functionality and what barriers prevent its implementation we find ourselves in a self-isolating area of research, expanding in justification but lacking in implementation. The benefits and commercial gain that a product development organisation can expect when designing for users' emotional needs is clearly vast and rewarding. Advocates of design and emotion are responsible for the task of enabling the engineering design practitioner to develop supra-functional/functional products.

Products fulfil many needs in today's consumer market above and beyond the pragmatic functional expectation. They can be designed to provoke a pleasant experience; either through user interaction or enjoyment gained through ownership. There is no doubt that usability is fundamental and very much a function of the engineering design practitioner. Design engineers directly influence the user's experience with technology.

When the engineering professions embrace the supra-functional aspects of design and emotion more fully, then engineering design education may reflect and respond to the paradigm shift from functional to functional/supra-functional products.

Design curricula in higher education rarely include design research as a set of skills with extremely high strategic value. Designers need to understand the tools of research, how they are deployed, how they map onto the various stages in the design process, and how research findings can contribute to both innovative and evolutionary design practice. (Laurel 2003)

The International Standards Organisation (ISO 2000) stipulates that product development teams' shall determine the design and development stages, appropriate reviews, verification and validation. It is required that inputs relating to the product shall be determined by the team, including functional performance requirements, applicable statutory and regulatory requirements and other items essential for design and development. This guide leaves the engineering design team free to create their own designing process within these guidelines. The standard requests functional performance requirements to be detailed and makes no comment on usability and designing for supra-functionality.

Both supra-functionality and functionality are necessary for a balanced product. They must be perceived as inter-connected. In most cases it is actually the products function to provoke a particular emotion and ensure a positive product experience for the user. A product that responds only to utilitarian needs may fail to develop user-product bonding, which is an important factor in enhancing the user experience, developing brand loyalty and market success.

Case study

A focus group discussion was conducted within the engineering department at PIPS Technology Limited (UK). PIPS began to develop traffic camera technology in the early 1990's with the patented development of pulsed, narrow wavelength retro-reflective techniques for image capture. They specialise in traffic related video imaging and licence plate capture technology. Current operation centres include offices in Chandler's Ford, Hampshire (United Kingdom) and Knoxville, Tennessee (USA).

The first named author acted as the group moderator with a sequence of set questions and discussion stimulus. The group consisted of six design engineers comprising of a Technical Director of engineering, Principal design engineer, Senior hardware design engineer,

Graphical user interface-software design engineer, Mechanical design engineer and Sales executive. Table 1 provides a profile of each of the purposively sampled participants.

TITLE	M/F	Birth Date	Years Experience	Professional experience	Professional recognition
Technical Director	M	1952	32	Homeland security, law enforcement ANPR Technology (Automatic Number Plate Recognition)	BSc, PhD
Quality and Principal Engineer	M	1945	39	Ministry of Defence special projects manager	BSc, MSc, CEng MIEE
Graphical User Interface (GUI) Engineer	M	1942	42	WEB interface design. Explosion proof inspection equipment user software Aircraft navigation systems	MIEE
Senior Hardware Engineer	M	1954	30	Digital Electronics, Telecommunications, domestic to industrial goods	
Sales Executive	M	1970	14	Police force and public safety. Law enforcement technology sales	
Mechanical Design Engineer	M	1979	7	Mechanical design explosion proof equipment. Roadside furniture. Consumer products, ANPR mechanical enclosure and system architecture.	MDes, MIED, IEng

Table 1: Participant profiles

Each participant was selected on the basis of engineering design knowledge, experience and opinions towards supra-functionality. The group’s engineering design experience is extensive and ranges from every day consumer products to Ministry of Defence and Homeland Security products and systems.

Focus group

Qualitative and quantitative data was gathered through the use of a focus group session and survey. The focus group discussion was video recorded for in-depth analysis and extraction of relevant views and comments from the group. One of the key benefits of focus group discussion and activity is the synergetic effect that can support the sharing of participants’ feelings, experiences and aspirations. Body language, facial expressions and vocal tone can help the researcher to interpret the findings more accurately.

The focus group was facilitated through a set of open-ended questions and statements that the participants discussed among themselves, sharing their views and opinions with the group.

Questions included the following: -

Focus Group Questions

- 1 Can you describe something in your home/office that annoys you?
Can you describe a cherished item?
 - 2 How do you currently gain user empathy?
 - 3 What are your views on user-centred design in engineering organisations?
 - 4 What approaches do you think one could take to elicit user requirements and needs?
 - 5 How do you review and communicate your ideas to the end user?
Do you hold design reviews for inter-team and customer/consumer communication?
 - 6 What value can be added by spending time in the identification of consumer usability, cognitive and emotional requirements?
 - 7 What are your thoughts on the design approaches currently taken within engineering companies to develop user empathy?
 - 8 How would you justify the inclusion or exclusion of supra-functionality in the design process and its introduction into the overall design brief and specification?
 - 9 What are your views on design for emotional response and a particular user experience?
 - 10 How would you improve the design engineers' role in designing effectively for the end user?
 - 11 In a single sentence what is your view on the added value of user empathy in engineering design?
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Table 2: Focus group questions

Focus group results have been divided into two groups and broken down into two themes, practical and philosophical. The following section represents the views expressed by the participants.

Practical

- The design engineers were concerned that they have limited methods and techniques to elicit user needs when designing for a user experience.

- Consumer feedback is elicited by the sales team and noted that most user contact took place towards the end of a development cycle, described by one participant as “Carving usability on at the end.”
- Part of the engineering designer’s role is to demonstrate user empathy taking into account emotional needs of the consumer.
- Although designing for a user experience would take time at the onset of a project it was identified that a user-centred approach results in a better product and increased sales.
- They take a technology-centred approach with a prime focus on getting the product to work in the laboratory environment with limited consideration for supra-functionality.
- Products are rarely reviewed and communicated to potential users until it is too late; although design reviews are a common element of any design process. Evidence suggests that more emphasis is needed in this area.
- Regular design and usability reviews should take place before during and after the design cycle. “The thing that we never do and we should do is actually have a formal review of the usability. We have formal reviews of the engineering, reviews of the production, but nobody ever sits down and says how could I actually make it more appealing and easier to use?”
- There is a damaging effect if emotional and usability needs are considered too late in the design process. Far too often user feedback is only gained once a product has been sold, damaging both the company profile and future sales.
- Design engineers should actively field-test [with users] the products that they design.
- A series of training exercises would be necessary accompanied by an improved design review process.

Philosophical

- Design engineers appreciate the need and recognised the importance of supra-functionality. “We need to start mapping our technology into something the user understands.”
- The group reported having received negative consumer responses to particular high-end technology products experiencing usability barriers. It was expressed that if the “User [is] force fed [that is] not user centred.”
- Concerns were raised that as engineering organisations continue to focus on technology led projects, little attention is being paid towards the user’s emotional needs.

- Positive feedback is often gained not through technical functionality but ‘excitement’ and ‘delight’ through product use, placing more emphasis on user needs.
- Supra-functionality should be an integral part of the design brief and functional specification as a tangible item or deliverable that creates the desired emotional engagement.
- Designing for an emotional response or need is “Definitely important. It’s almost impossible to measure or quantify, I think it’s different in different market sectors, making complex equipment look sexy. It’s brilliant, it really is.”
- Products that considered aesthetics and product semantics often resulted in more attractive, less complex and approachable technology.
- Low technology products often have a better emotional response than high technology items. Only due to the integral simplicity rather than actually being designed for ease of use.

When asked, “In a single sentence what is your view on the added value of Supra-functionality?” The following replies were given:

“If a customer buys 500 units from us, they’re not going to buy 500 units that often. The crunch line is: would they buy 500 if they had another 500 to buy? So the added value is that they would buy it again. And the user empathy will directly affect that.”

“I think for me having user empathy is that every time I use it I get a warm glow from it. If you’ve got empathy with it you never lose the fun of using it. Every time you use it, you think I’m glad I bought that, I made the right choice, so you re-enforce the decision you took. I think it’s just the opposite when it doesn’t work properly. It winds you up so much. So I think that’s the value every time you use it [a successful product] you still get this warm glow.”

Survey

Quantitative data was gathered through a survey to elicit specific views towards design and emotion, such as the expectation of training requirements and added value of supra-functionality, preparation for successful integration, re-evaluation of the design engineer’s role and rating the importance of designing for a user experience. These questions and

statements as shown were rated against a scale of seven (1= strongly disagree to 7 = strongly agree) with the average value assigned to each comment in Table 3.

Survey Results	Scale
How important do you find the emotional domain?	5
Rate the importance of adopting a user centred design approach	6.25
Products need to satisfy needs beyond functional	5.75
Functionality alone does not guarantee acceptance, purchase or use	6.5
Part of the Design Engineers role is to demonstrate user/consumer empathy	5.75
Adopting a user centred approach, designing for emotion and user experience is time consuming with limited value	2.75
The integration of supra-functionality to engineering products can be easily integrated into the existing design process	4.5
Engineers will be reluctant to embrace design and emotion as a fundamental element of successful engineering design	4.5
To successfully integrate user centred design and emotionally aware engineering products requires significant training, a well developed and constant design review process.	5.5

Table 3: Questions and averaged scores

Questions were designed to encourage and stimulate conversation, to expand upon current views and themes within the engineering profession and how these certain approaches or modes of design would effect their engineering design practice.

Discussion

The case study appears to support the authors' concerns that design engineers demonstrate little consideration in designing for emotional and usability needs. However, the engineering designers expressed a significant appreciation for the added value of supra-functionality in the engineering design process.

The case study identified that limited consideration for user needs is not due to reluctance in embracing emotional aspects of design; but that engineering designers perceive that they do

not have the tools to elicit user needs and so remain isolated from the end user. Bruseburg and McDonagh-Philp (2002) found that industrial designers shared this perception. Designers are developing research tools for designers. There is no reason why design engineers cannot adopt, adapt and develop such approaches and methods.

Cross (2000) refers to "listening to the voice of the customer" (p. 107), but as customers (users) say one thing, do another and possibly feel something else, listening alone may not be enough. It is increasingly important for product developers (Design engineer, Industrial designer, manufacturer) to become as intimate with the users as possible. One cannot substitute another person's experience, but increased empathy, understanding and awareness can lead to more effective designs.

Simple technology-led products developed through the engineering design organisation are often easy to use, not due to a user-centred approach but because of their intrinsic simplicity. The products ease of use is often a result of chance rather than a supra-functional product.

This study has highlighted that as technology-led organisations continue to progress and develop, more emphasis must be placed on designing for a particular user experience. As an engineering design organisation grows there comes a point when supra-functionality must be considered in its own right. As one participant commented, if the "user is force fed" then it is not user-centred design.

As technology advances, the ability to successfully map new technology into a usable interface becomes increasingly difficult. The study indicated that user empathy is still very much considered towards the end of a development cycle, resulting in adding on usability rather than integrating it within the process. The participants felt that to effectively design emotionally responsive products would require significant training accompanied by a well-developed and constant design review process.

Engineering designers tend to take a technology-centred approach with a prime focus on getting the product to work in a laboratory environment. As a consequence the discussion noted that these technology-led decisions begin to define product architecture and demonstrate little user consideration.

It would be more beneficial if design engineers were more involved in eliciting user feedback rather than relying on pre-filtered data from the sales and marketing departments. The design engineer may rely solely on the pre-filtered data, which may not accurately reflect user needs.

It was felt that adopting a supra-functional approach into the existing design process would add significant value. Although designing for a user experience would take time at the onset of a project it was identified that supra-functional consideration would result in better products and increased sales.

Summary

The role of the design engineer is up for review. Technology led organisations need to focus on an alternative skill-set to achieve global market success. This study clearly identified a need for the engineering design profession to embrace supra-functional design.

As technology evolves and further dislocates itself from the consumer's basic understanding, design engineers are responsible for mapping complex details into a usable interface and product experience. Technical functionality alone does not substantiate market success. Empathy towards human cognitive, physical and emotional needs must now be considered and integrated within the designing process. In order to develop a supra-functional product, training and educational requirements have been identified as a requirement for the engineering design practitioner.

Recommendations

Training for the engineer needs to consist of designing for a user experience, usability testing, verbal and non-verbal communication skills. These interpersonal skills will strengthen the bond between engineering design and sales departments also enabling the design engineer to actively participate and conduct focus group research where interaction and communication with the end user is of extreme importance. These skills enable the elicitation, probing, guiding and redirection of group discussion to extract the most useful data.

Formal training on conducting focus groups and usability reviews that coincide with the existing engineering review process was identified as being beneficial. Supra-functionality

may be implemented as part of a trilateral review process supporting the development and review of Design, Usability and Manufacture.

Usability testing, scenario evaluation, product role-play including other research and evaluation methods need to be conducted both internally and externally by the design engineer and user groups. An external usability test house only postpones the design engineer gaining first hand experience, insight and empathy with users. Implementation of iterative review processes, user testing and qualitative research techniques would support more effective product outcomes, based on increased empathy and awareness.

The added value of supra-functional consideration can be significant but requires effort and support from the engineering and design organisations. There is a fundamental difference between knowing and doing. The knowing and doing problem can be described as “The challenge of turning knowledge about how to enhance organisational performance into actions consistent with that knowledge” as discussed by Holdway and Walker (2004).

It is time for the engineering designer to elicit user needs, both technical and emotional. Negotiation and discussion techniques must be adopted to generate the necessary data. The design engineer and salesperson must work closely together on new research and development projects. It may be suggested that a specific role be identified to consider supra-functional user needs; a role often played by industrial designers in the design team.

To conclude, the small sample of design engineers appeared receptive to adopting a supra-functional approach and willing to embrace new skills and techniques in designing for a positive user experience.

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